

**CRYOspheric STudies of Atmospheric Trends
in stratospherically and radiatively important gases**

**An RTD Project in the European Commission
Fifth Framework Programme
EVK2-2001-00116**

**Abridged Executive Summary of the Final
Report**

1 January 2002 – 31 December 2005

incorporating the 4th Annual Report
for the period 1 January – 31 December 2005

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AC3 National Center for Atmospheric Research (UCAR-NCAR) [Retired during 2005]

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CR9 Max Planck Institute for Chemistry (MPG)

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AC10 Max-Planck-Institut fuer Kernphysik (MPIK) [Replaced Open University in 2005]

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AC11 Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO) [Reclassified from Subcontractor SB11 to Assistant Contractor AC11 in 2005]

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SB12 British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC)

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SECTION 2: EXECUTIVE PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY RELATED TO THE LAST (12 MONTH) REPORTING PERIOD

See Executive Summary for entire project in Section 5.

Publications (cumulative list)

Peer Reviewed Articles:

Authors	Date	Title	Journal	Reference
Assonov S.S., Brenninkmeijer C.A.M., Jöckel P., Mulvaney R., Bernard S., Chappellaz J.	2006	A reconstruction of the past trend of atmospheric CO based on firn air samples from Berkner Island, Antarctica	Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics Discussions	5, 10259-10299 SRef-ID: 1680-7375/acpd/2005-5-10259
Bernard S., Röckmann T., Kaiser J., Barnola J.M., Fischer H., Blunier T., Chappellaz J.	2006	Constraints on N ₂ O budget changes since pre-industrial time from new firn air and ice core isotope measurements	Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics	6, 1-11
Henderson L., Clark I.D., Chappellaz J., Fisher D., Koerner R., Worthy D.E.J., Kotzer T., Norman A.L	2006	CO ₂ isotopes as tracers of firn air diffusion and age in an Arctic glacier with summer melting	Journal of Geophysical Research - Atmospheres.	In press
Huber, C., M. Leuenberger, R. Spahni, J. Flückiger, J. Schwander, T.F. Stocker, S.J. Johnsen, A. Landais, and J. Jouzel	2006	Isotope calibrated Greenland temperature record over Marine Isotope Stage 3 and its relation to CH ₄	Earth and Planetary Science Letters	In press
Huber, C., U. Beyerle, M. Leuenberger, J. Schwander, R. Kipfer, R. Spahni, J.P. Severinghaus, K. Weiler	2006	Evidence for molecular size dependent gas fractionation in firn air derived from noble gases, oxygen, and nitrogen measurements	Earth and Planetary Science Letters	243, 61 - 73
Assonov, S.S., C.A.M. Brenninkmeijer	2005	On the N ₂ O correction used for mass-spectrometric analysis of atmospheric CO ₂	Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry	submitted
Assonov, S.S., C.A.M. Brenninkmeijer	2005	Reporting small $\Delta^{17}\text{O}$ values: existing definitions and concepts	Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry	19(5): 627-636 doi: 10.1002/rcm.1833
Assonov, S.S., C.A.M. Brenninkmeijer, P. Jöckel	2005	The ¹⁸ O isotope exchange rate between firn air CO ₂ and the firn matrix at three Antarctic sites	Journal of Geophysical Research - Atmospheres.	110, D18310, 10.1029/2005JD005769
Forster, P.M. de F., J.B. Burkholder, C. Clerbaux, P.F. Coheur, M. Dutta, L.K. Gohar, M.D. Hurley, G. Myhre, R.W. Portmann, K.P. Shine, T.J. Wallington, D. Wuebbles	2005	Resolving the uncertainties in the radiative forcing of HFC-134a	Journal of Quantative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer	93 (4), 447 - 460
Huber, C., and M. Leuenberger	2005	On-line systems for continuous water and gas isotope ratio measurements	Isotopes in Environmental and Health Studies	41 (3), 189-205 10.1080/10256010500229942

Authors	Date	Title	Journal	Reference
Hurley, M. D., T. J. Wallington, G. A. Buchanan, L. K. Gohar, G. Marston, K. P. Shine	2005	IR spectrum and radiative forcing of CF ₄ revisited	Journal of Geophysical Research - Atmospheres.	110, D02102, 10.1029/2004JD005201
Landais, A., V. Masson-Delmotte, J. Jouzel, D. Raynaud, S. Johnsen, M. Leuenberger, J. Schwander, B. Minster	2005	The glacial inception recorded in the NorthGRIP Greenland ice core: information from air isotopic measurements	Climate Dynamics	26 (2-3), 273 - 284
Leuenberger, M.	2005	Stabile Isotope in polaren Eisbohrkernen enthalten klimarelevante Information	<i>In</i> Auf Spurensuche in der Natur: Stabile Isotope in der ökologischen Forschung,	<i>Ed.</i> Prof. Dr. K. Auerswald und Prof. Dr. W. Haber, pp. 174, Verlag Dr. Friedrich Pfeil, München
Pupek, M., S.S. Assonov, J. Mühle, T.S. Rhee, D.E. Oram, C. Koepfel, F. Slemr, C.A.M. Brenninkmeijer	2005	Isotope analysis of hydrocarbons: trapping, recovering and archiving hydrocarbons and halocarbons separated from ambient air	Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry	19, 1–6 doi: 10.1002/rcm.1812
Reeves, C.E. W. T. Sturges, G. A. Sturrock, K. Preston, D. E. Oram, J. Schwander, R. Mulvaney, J. -M. Barnola, J. Chappellaz	2005	Trends of halon gases in polar firm air: implication for their emission distributions	Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics	Vol. 5, pp 2055-2064
Sowers T., S. Bernard S. O. Aballain, J. Chappellaz, J.-M.Barnola, T. Marik	2005	Records of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of atmospheric CH ₄ over the last two centuries as recorded in Antarctic snow and ice,	Global Biogeochemical Cycles	19, GB2002, doi:10.1029/2004GB002408
Worton, D. R, Sturges, W. T., Schwander, J., Mulvaney, R., Barnola, J-M., Chappellaz, J.	2005	20 th Century trends and budget implications of trihalomethanes and dihalomethanes inferred from North GRIP firm air	Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics Discussions	6, 701-754 SRef-ID: 1680-7375/acpd/2006-6-701
Gohar, L.K., G. Myhre, K.P. Shine	2004	Updated radiative forcing estimates of four halocarbons	Journal of Geophysical Research - Atmospheres.	109, D01107, 10.1029/2003JD004320
Huber, C. and M. Leuenberger	2004	Measurements of Isotope and Elemental Ratios of Air from Polar Ice with a New On-Line Extraction Method	Geochemistry Geophysics Geosystems	5 (10), Q10002, doi:10.1029/2004GC000766
Landais, A., J.-M. Barnola, V. Masson-Delmotte, J. Jouzel, J. Chappellaz, N. Caillon, C. Huber, M. Leuenberger, S. Johnsen	2004	A continuous record of temperature evolution over a whole sequence of Dansgaard-Oeschger during Marine Isotopic Stage 4 (76 to 62 kyr BP):	Geophysical Research Letters	31 (22): art. no. L22211

Authors	Date	Title	Journal	Reference
Landais, A., N. Caillon, J. Jouzel, J. Chappellaz, A. Grachev, C. Goujon, J.M. Barnola, and M. Leuenberger	2004	A method for precise quantification of temperature change and phasing between temperature and methane increases through gas measurements on Dansgaard-Oeschger event 12 (-45 kyr)	Earth and Planetary Sciences Letters	225, 221-232
Landais, A., N. Caillon, J. Severinghaus, J-M. Barnola, C. Goujon, J. Jouzel, V. Masson-Delmotte	2004	Analyse isotopique de l'air piégé dans la glace pour quantifier les variations de température Comptes rendus de l'académie des sciences	Geoscience	336, 963-970
Trudinger, C. M., D.M. Etheridge, G.A. Sturrock, P.J. Fraser, P.B. Krummel, A. McCulloch	2004	Atmospheric histories of halocarbons from analysis of Antarctic firn air: methyl bromide, methyl chloride, chloroform, and dichloromethane.	Journal of Geophysical Research – Atmospheres	109 (D22): 22310, doi:10.1029/2004JD004932.
Assonov, S.S., C.A.M. Brenninkmeijer	2003	A re-determination of absolute values for $^{17}\text{R}_{\text{VPDB-CO}_2}$ and $^{17}\text{R}_{\text{VSMOW}}$,	Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry	17(10), 1017-1029.
Assonov, S.S., C.A.M. Brenninkmeijer	2003	On the ^{17}O correction for CO_2 mass spectrometric isotopic analysis	Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry	17(10), 1007-1016.
Huber, C., M. Leuenberger, O. Zumbrennen	2003	Continuous extraction of trapped air from bubble ice or water for on-line determination of isotope ratios	Analytical Chemistry	75, 2324-2332
Huber, C., M. Leuenberger	2003	Fast high-precision on-line determination of hydrogen isotope ratios of water or ice by continuous-flow isotope ratio mass spectrometry	Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry	17, 1319-1325
Röckmann, T., J. Kaiser, C.A.M. Brenninkmeijer	2003	The isotopic fingerprint of the pre-industrial and the anthropogenic N_2O source	Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics	3, 315-323
Steil, B., C. Brühl, E. Manzini, P.J. Crutzen, J. Lelieveld, P.J. Rasch, E. Roeckner, and K. Krüger	2003	A new interactive chemistry climate model. I: Present day climatology and interannual variability of the middle atmosphere using the model and 9 years of HALOE/UARS data	Journal of Geophysical Research	108, 4290, doi: 10.1029/2002JD002971
Trudinger, C. M., P.J. Rayner, I.G. Enting, M. Heimann, M. Scholze	2003	Implications of ice core smoothing for inferring CO_2 flux variability	Journal of Geophysical Research - Atmospheres	108 (D16): 4492, doi:10.1029/2003JD003562.
Leuenberger, M. and C. Huber	2002	On-line determination of oxygen isotope ratios of water or ice by mass spectrometry	Analytical Chemistry	74, 4611-4617
Sturrock, G. A., D. M. Etheridge, C. M. Trudinger, P. J. Fraser and A.M. Smith	2002	Atmospheric histories of halocarbons from analysis of Antarctic firn air: Major Montreal Protocol species	Journal of Geophysical Research – Atmospheres.	107(D24): doi 10.1029/2002JD002545
Trudinger, C. M., D. M. Etheridge, P. J. Rayner, I. G. Enting, G. A Sturrock, R. L. Langenfelds	2002	Reconstructing atmospheric histories from measurements of air composition in firn	Journal of Geophysical Research - Atmospheres.	107 (D24), doi 10.1029/2002JD002548

Non refereed literature:

Authors / Editors	Date	Title	Event	Reference	Type
Assonov, S.S., Brenninkmeijer, C.A.M., Chappellaz, J.	2006	A reconstruction of the past trend of atmospheric CO based on firn air samples from Berkner Island, Antarctica	European Geophysical Union, Vienna	EGU06-A-10581	Abstract & oral
Barnola, J-M., Schwander, J., Martinerie, P., Weiler, K., Sturges, W.	2006	Comparison of the different firn diffusion models of the CRYOSTAT project	European Geophysical Union, Vienna	EGU06-A-02896	Abstract & poster
Etheridge, D., Trudinger, C., Langenfelds, R., Steele, P., Ferretti, D., Smith, A.	2006	Increase in carbon monoxide concentration in the southern hemisphere over the past century (solicited)	European Geophysical Union, Vienna	EGU06-A-05447	Abstract & oral
Leuenberger, M., Severinghaus, J.P., Schwander, J., Spahni, R., Battle, M., Huber, C., Beyerle, U., Kipfer, R., Weiler, K.	2006	Molecular size dependent gas fractionation in firn air derived from noble gases, oxygen, and nitrogen measurements	European Geophysical Union, Vienna	EGU06-A-02859	Abstract & oral
Leuenberger, M.L., Weiler, K., Kipfstuhl, S., Schwander, J., Nyfeler, P., Landais, A., Jouzel, J., Mulvaney, R.	2006	Comparison of new firn sample results from Kohlen station with those from the 300 km apart firn sampling in Dronning Maud Land in 1998	European Geophysical Union, Vienna	EGU06-A-05554	Abstract & poster
MacFarling Meure, C., Etheridge, D., van Ommen, T., Steele, P., Langenfelds, R., Trudinger, C.	2006	Law Dome trace gas records extended to 2000 years BP	European Geophysical Union, Vienna	EGU06-A-10579	Abstract & poster
Martinerie, P., Nourtier-Mazauric, E.; Barnola, J-M., Sturges, W., Worton, D. R., Atlas, E., Brasseur, G.	2006	Halocarbon trends and budgets over the last century : a model study constrained by firn air data	European Geophysical Union, Vienna	EGU06-A-02575	Abstract & oral
Sturges, W., Worton, D., Atlas, E., Stroud, V., Johnson, K., Schwander, J., Barnola, JM., Chappellaz, J.	2006	An atmospheric history of alkyl nitrates and alkanes in firn air: an indication of increasing NO _x in the Northern Hemisphere	European Geophysical Union, Vienna	EGU06-A-02721	Abstract & poster
Weiler, K., Schwander, J., Nyfeler, P., Leuenberger, M., Kaufmann, P., Stoof, G., Trimborn, K., Freitag, J., Kipfstuhl, S.	2006	Firn air sampling at Kohlen Station, Antarctica: estimation of the age difference between air and ice from CO ₂ data	European Geophysical Union, Vienna	EGU06-A-02879	Abstract & poster
Worton, D. R., Sturges, W. T., Etheridge, D., Macfarling Meure, C., Humphrey, S. P., Begley, P., Schwander, J., Mulvaney, R.	2006	Atmospheric trends of CF ₄ and C ₂ F ₆ inferred from air recovered from polar firn and ice.	European Geophysical Union, Vienna	EGU06-A-02398	Abstract & oral

Authors / Editors	Date	Title	Event	Reference	Type
E. Nourtier-Mazauric, P. Martinerie, J.-M. Barnola, W. Sturges, D.R. Worton, E. Atlas, G. Brasseur	2005	Twentieth century atmospheric halocarbon trends: comparison of model results with atmospheric and firn air data sets	European Geophysical Union, Vienna	Geophysical Research Abstracts, Vol. 7, 08005	Abstract & poster
Weiler, K., J., Schwander M. Leuenberger, P. Nyfeler, F. Valentino, R. Spahni, R. Mulvaney, P. Anderson, R. Salmon, J. Severinghaus	2005	Annual trace gas variations in Halley firn: Effects of diffusion and advection on a multi-proxy data set	European Geophysical Union, Vienna	Geophysical Research Abstracts, Vol. 7, 03632	Abstract & oral
Worton, D. R., Sturges, W. T., Begley, P., Salmon, R., Mulvaney, R., Atlas, E.	2005	Seasonal cycles of halocarbons and alkyl nitrates at Halley, Antarctica	European Geophysical Union, Vienna	Geophysical Research Abstracts, Vol. 7, 09561	Abstract & Poster
Worton, D. R.	2005	Alkyl nitrates (C ₁ -C ₅), trihalomethanes and related compounds in contemporary air and air preserved in polar firn and ice		Ph.D. from the University of East Anglia, UK.	Ph.D. Thesis
Barnola, J.-M., R. Pieritz, C. Goujon, P. Duval, E. Boller	2004	3D Reconstruction of the Vostok firn structure by X-ray tomography.	XIII Glaciological Symposium 24-28/05/2004 St. Petersburg	Mater. Glyatsiol. Issled	Abstract & oral
Bernard, S., T. Roeckmann, J. Kaiser, J. Chappellaz, J.-M. Barnola, C.A.M. Brenninkmeijer	2004	Changes of methane and nitrous oxide in the atmosphere : new constraints from stable isotope analyses in polar firn and ice	European Geophysical Union, Nice	Geophysical Research Abstracts, Vol. 6, 01450	Abstract & oral
Bernard, Sophie	2004	Atmospheric CH ₄ and N ₂ O evolution: Constraint from their stable isotopes analysis in polar firn and ice cores		PhD from the University Joseph-Fourier, Grenoble I	Ph.D. Thesis
Brenninkmeijer, C.A.M., S.S. Assonov, C. Koepfel, R. Mulvaney, S. Bernard, W. Sturges	2004	Reconstructing past carbon monoxide mixing ratios using antarctic firn air and isotope analysis	European Geosciences Union, Nice	Geophysical Research Abstracts, Vol. 6, 04212, 2004	Abstract and Abstract & poster
Dreyfus, G., K. Kawamura, A. Landais, N. Caillon, J. Jouzel, V. Masson-Delmotte, B. Minster, J.-M. Barnola, T. Nakazawa, S. Aoki,	2004	The isotopic composition of trapped air in four Antarctic ice cores: Comparing measurements with model predictions,	European Geophysical Union meeting, Nice	Geophysical Research Abstracts, Vol. 6, 04319	Abstract & poster
Etheridge, D. M., C.M. Trudinger, L.P. Steele, R.L. Langenfelds, P.J. Fraser, G.A. Sturrock, D. Ferretti, K. Lassey, A.M. Smith, M. Battle, T. van Ommen	2004	Natural and anthropogenic emissions of methane, halomethanes and carbon monoxide over the past century found from firn air.	8th International Global Atmospheric Chemistry Conference: Christchurch, NZ.	The Conference. Handbook p. 25	Abstract & oral

Authors / Editors	Date	Title	Event	Reference	Type
Huber, C.	2004	How large were the temperature fluctuations in Greenland over the last 70'000 years? New insights from stable isotope ratio measurements on polar ice cores with a novel on-line extraction technique.		PhD thesis, Physics Institute, University of Bern, Bern	Ph.D. Thesi
Huber, C.; U. Beyerle, M. Leuenberger, J. Schwander, R. Spahni, R. Kipfer	2004	Evidence for size dependent gas fractionation in firn air derived from noble gases, O ₂ , and N ₂ measurements	European Geophysical Union meeting, Nice	EGU04-A-02761; AS3.13-1TH3P-0495	Abstract & poster
Landais A., J.M. Barnola, N. Caillon, D. Dahl-Jensen, S. Johnsen, J. Jouzel, V. Masson-Delmotte, B. Minster.	2004	The rapid climatic variability in the northern hemisphere during the glacial inception as inferred from air isotopic measurements on a new Greenland ice core, NorthGRIP,	European Geophysical Union meeting, Nice.	Geophysical Research Abstracts, Vol. 6, 01757	Abstract & oral
Leuenberger, M.; C. Huber, J. Schwander	2004	Correlation of convective zone and H ₂ O isotope temperature sensitivity deduced from N ₂ isotope measurements and firn modelling	European Geophysical Union, Nice	EGU04-A-03348; AS3.13-1WE3O-005	Abstract & oral
Martinerie, P. J.-M. Barnola, W. Sturges, D.R. Worton, E. Atlas, G. Brousseau	2004	A model study of halocarbon concentrations during the twentieth century using firn air data	European Geophysical Union, Nice	Geophysical Research Abstracts, Vol. 6, 03374	Abstract & oral
Sturges, W.T.; D.R. Worton, D.A. Wylding, R. Mulvaney, S. Bernard	2004	Trace gases in firn air from Berkner Island, Antarctica	European Geophysical Union meeting, Nice	EGU04-A-02134; AS3.13-1TH3P-0497	Abstract & poster
Trudinger, C. M., D.M. Etheridge, P.J. Fraser, P.B. Krummel, G.A. Sturrock,	2004	Law Dome firn reconstructions of methyl bromide, methyl chloride, chloroform and dichloromethane	European Geosciences Union, Nice	Geophysical Research Abstracts, 6: 07407	Abstract & poster
Trudinger, C.M., D.M. Etheridge, P.J. Fraser, P.B. Krummel, R.L. Langenfelds, C.E. Allison, L.P. Steele, L.W. Porter, I. Levin, J. Harnisch, J.	2004	Long-term trends in the concentration and emissions of CF ₄ , SF ₆ , methyl bromide, methyl chloride, chloroform and dichloromethane.	Cape Grim Baseline Air Pollution Station Annual Science	Meeting, : abstracts, CSIRO Atmospheric Research Aspendale, Vic.: CSIRO Atmospheric Research. p. 27.	Abstract & oral
Weiler, K; J. Schwander, M. Leuenberger, C. Huber, R. Spahni, P. Nyfeler, S. Bernard, R. Mulvaney, R. Salmon	2004	Seasonal gas diffusion in the upper firn strata	European Geophysical Union, Nice	Geophysical Research Abstracts, Vol. 6 http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EGU04/05654/EGU04-J-05654.pdf	Abstract & oral

Authors / Editors	Date	Title	Event	Reference	Type
D. R. Worton, W. T. Sturges, J. Schwander, R. Mulvaney, J. Chappellaz, J.-M. Barnola, E. Atlas	2004	Measurements of short chain (C ₁ -C ₅) alkyl mononitrates and related compounds in North GRIP firn air.	AGU San Francisco	Abstract #A22C-06	Abstract & oral
Worton, D. R. W.T. Sturges, J. Schwander, J. Chappellaz, J.-M. Barnola.	2004	Atmospheric trends of brominated halomethanes and chloroform inferred from northern hemisphere firn air.	European Geophysical Union, Nice	Geophysical Research Abstracts, Vol. 6, 04818,	Abstract & oral
Bernard, S., J. Kaiser, T. Röckmann, J. Chappellaz, J-M. Barnola, C.A.M. Brenninkmeijer	2003	Changes of methane and nitrous oxide in the atmosphere : New constraints from stable isotope analyses in polar firn and ice	AGU San Francisco	Eos Trans. AGU, 84(46), Fall Meet. Suppl., Abstract A42D-08	Abstract & oral
Beyerle, U., M. Leuenberger, J. Schwander and R. Kipfer	2003	Noble gas evidence for gas fractionation in firn	Kurashiki, Japan Goldschmidt Conference	Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta, 67(18), A38	Abstract & oral
Gohar LK, K.P. Shine	2003	The radiative impact of uncertainties in perfluoromethane absorption measurements.	EGS-AGU-EUG Joint Assembly, Nice	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EAE03/06538/EAE03-J-06538.pdf	Abstract & oral
Gohar LK, K.P. Shine	2003	The radiative impact of uncertainties in halocarbon absorption measurements using CF ₄ as an example.	Royal Meteorological Society National Conference, University of East Anglia, England	http://www.metlink.org/conf2003/detail.php?recordID=194	Abstract & oral
Huber C., M. Leuenberger	2003	Assessing the rapid temperature changes of D/O events 9 to 12 from air isotope measurements on North GRIP Ice Using a New On-line Technique	AGU 2003, San Francisco,	Eos Trans. AGU, 84(46), Fall Meet. Suppl., Abstract PP42A-0852, 2003	Abstract & oral
Huber, C. M. Leuenberger, P. Nyfeler	2003	New online methods for water and air isotopes on ice cores	EGS 2003, Nice	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EAE03/08250/EAE03-J-08250.pdf	Abstract & oral
Landais A., J.-M. Barnola, C. Goujon, N. Caillon, J. Jouzel, J. Chappellaz, S. Johnsen, D. Dahl-Jensen	2003	Quantification of surface temperature changes during rapid climatic events 18-20 from air isotopic measurements in NorthGRIP ice cores and precise phasing with CH ₄ variations	San Feliu de Guixols, Spain	Euroconference on the Comparison of Ice Core Records with Marine Sediment and Climate Models	Abstract & oral
Landais A., J.M. Barnola, C. Goujon, N. Caillon, J. Jouzel, J. Chappellaz, S. Johnsen, D. Dahl-Jensen,	2003	Quantification of surface temperature changes during rapid climatic events 18-20 from air isotopic measurements in NorthGRIP ice cores and precise phasing with CH ₄ variations,	EGS-AGU-EUG Joint Assembly, Nice	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EAE03/01885/EAE03-J-01885-1.pdf	Abstract & oral

Authors / Editors	Date	Title	Event	Reference	Type
Landais A., J.M. Barnola, C. Goujon, N. Caillon, J. Jouzel, J. Chappellaz, S. Johnsen, D. Dahl-Jensen	2003	Quantification of surface temperature changes during rapid climatic events 18-20 from air isotopic measurements in NorthGRIP ice cores and precise phasing with CH ₄ variations	American Geophysical Union, San Francisco	Eos Trans. AGU, 84(46), Fall Meet. Suppl., Abstract PP42A-0853	Abstract & poster
Landais A., N. Caillon, J.P. Severinghaus, J. Jouzel, V. Masson-Delmotte	2003	Analyses isotopiques à haute précision de l'air piégé dans les glaces polaires pour la quantification des variations rapides de température: Méthode et limites		Notes des Activités Instrumentales de l'IPSL	Note n°39
Mak, J.E., S. Bernard, J. Chappellaz	2003	An experimental technique to measure carbon monoxide isotopes in small air samples and in ice cores	EGS-AGU-EUG Joint Assembly, Nice	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EAE03/05005/EAE03-J-05005.pdf	Abstract & poster
Mulvaney, R., S. Bernard, M. Leuenberger	2003	Extraction of firm air from Berkner Island, Antarctica	7th International Symposium on Antarctic Glaciology, Milan		Abstract & poster
Sturges, W.T., D.E. Oram, G.A. Sturrock, R. Mulvaney, J. Chappellaz, J.-M. Barnola, J. Schwander, C.A.M. Brenninkmeijer	2003	Trends in climatically-important trace gases derived from measurements of polar firm air	Royal Met Soc., Norwich, UK	http://www.metlink.org/conf2003/detail.php?pageNum_abstracts=6&totalRows_abstracts=413&recordID=315	Abstract & oral
Aballain, O.	2002	Reconstruction de l'évolution passe du rapport isotopique ¹³ C/ ¹² C du methane atmospherique, a partir de l'analyse de l'air extrait du neve polaire		These de Doctorat de l'Université J. Fourier, Grenoble	PhD Thesis
Assonov, S., C.A.M. Brenninkmeijer, J.M. Barnola	2002	CO ₂ in Antarctic firm air: Oxygen exchange at firm conditions	EGS XXVII General Assembly	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EGS02/06272/EGS02-A-06272.pdf	Abstract & poster
Atlas, E., V. Stroud, K. Johnson, T. Sturges, J. Chappellaz, J. Schwander, J. Butler	2002	A history of C ₂ -C ₄ NMHC and related compounds in the atmosphere from firm air cores in the Northern and Southern Hemispheres	EGS XXVII General Assembly also AGU General Assembly	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EGS02/00757/EGS02-A-00757.pdf Eos Trans. AGU, 83(47), Fall Meet. Suppl., Abstract A72A-0137, 2002	Abstract & poster Abstract & poster
Etheridge, D.M., C. Trudinger, C. Lowe, K.R. Lassey, A.M. Smith, L.P. Steele, R.L. Langenfelds, R.J. Francey, M. Battle	2002	Evolution of atmospheric methane during the anthropocene from methane isotopic measurements of firm air from two Antarctic sites	EGS XXVII General Assembly	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EGS02/05157/EGS02-A-05157.pdf	Abstract & oral
Eyer, M., M. Leuenberger	2002	δ ¹³ C Measurements on air of small ice samples	EGS XXVII General Assembly	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EGS02/00026/EGS02-A-00026.pdf	Abstract & oral

Authors / Editors	Date	Title	Event	Reference	Type
Goujon, C., J.M. Barnola, C. Ritz, J. Chappellaz, R. Mulvaney	2002	Isotopic fractionation due to temperature gradients between the surface and the bottom of the firn	EGS XXVII General Assembly	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EGS02/04289/EGS02-A-04289.pdf	Abstract & oral
Huber, C., M. Leuenberger	2002	O ₂ /N ₂ Measurements on polar ice cores with a new on-line extraction technique	EGS XXVII General Assembly	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EGS02/00055/EGS02-A-00055.pdf	Abstract & poster
Landais, A., M. Leuenberger, N. Caillon, J. Schwander, J. Jouzel	2002	Isotope fractionation of modern air in Dome C (Antarctica) polar firn	EGS XXVII General Assembly	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EGS02/01190/EGS02-A-01190.pdf	Abstract & oral
Leuenberger, M., P. Nyfeler, J. Schwander	2002	Isotopic and elemental ratio measurements on air from North Grip firn air sampling 2001	EGS XXVII General Assembly	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EGS02/01399/EGS02-A-01399.pdf	Abstract & oral
Schwander, J., R. Spahni, M. Leuenberger	2002	Ventilation of upper firn strata	EGS XXVII General Assembly	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EGS02/03654/EGS02-A-03654.pdf	Abstract & poster
Sturges, W.T., C.E. Reeves, G.A. Sturrock, D.R. Worton, D.E. Oram, R. Mulvaney, J. Schwander, J. Chappellaz, J.-M. Barnola	2002	A 20th Century Record of Some Halogenated Organic Gases and COS in the Atmosphere	CACGP/IGAC 2002 Conference: "Atmospheric Chemistry within the Earth System: From Regional Pollution to Global Change"	http://atlas.chemistry.uoc.gr/abstracts/Abstract_&oral_presentations/Session_A/Sturges_et_al__S_A.doc	Abstract & oral
Sturrock, G.A., W.T. Sturges, C.M. Trudinger, D.M. Etheridge	2002	Histories of synthetic halocarbons from analysis of firn air	EGS XXVII General Assembly	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EGS02/03075/EGS02-A-03075.pdf	Abstract & oral
Worton, D.R., W.T. Sturges, J. Schwander, J. Chappellaz, E. Atlas, V. Stroud	2002	Methyl halides and related compounds in firn air at North Grip	EGS XXVII General Assembly	http://www.cosis.net/abstracts/EGS02/01379/EGS02-A-01379.pdf	Abstract & poster
Schwander, J.	2001	Firn Air Sampling: Field Report NORTH GRIP 2001		Internal report available from author at University of Berne, or from CRYOSTAT Coordinator	Report

Planning of future publications:

A number of papers are planned, and in particular are expected to arise from the 2006 Special Session dedicated to CRYOSTAT at the European Geosciences Union General Symposium 2 – 7 April 2006.

SECTION 4. TECHNOLOGICAL IMPLEMENTATION PLAN (CUMULATIVE)

Please see final electronic version on CORDIS website (e-tip page).

SECTION 5: EXECUTIVE SUMMARY RELATED TO THE OVERALL PROJECT DURATION

Contract n°	EVK2-2001-00116	Reporting period:	1 January 2002 – 31 December 2005
Title	CRYOspheric Studies of Atmospheric Trends in stratospherically and radiatively important gases – CRYOSTAT		
<p>Objectives:</p> <p>CRYOSTAT was conceived to undertake the first combined measurements of virtually all significant greenhouse gases (GHGs) (other than water vapour), ozone depleting substances (ODSs), and related trace gases in contiguous firn and ice profiles, spanning as much as 200 years, from both the northern and southern polar ice caps. For many gases this would represent the first attempt to measure their complete atmospheric histories from pre-industrial times to the present day. Using inter-linked computer models of both the transfer of gases from the atmosphere to firn and ice, and the atmospheric transport and chemistry of gases, it was aimed to reconstruct the evolution and distribution of these numerous gaseous species in the global atmosphere (hemispheric scale for the shorter-lived gases, inter-hemispheric and tropospheric-stratospheric distributions for the longer-lived gases). Sources and sinks, both natural and anthropogenic, were to be identified and quantified using novel multiple-isotope analyses, and by using trace gas modelling. These reconstructed trends were to be further used to determine the histories of (a) radiative forcing from the measured GHGs, (b) stratospheric ozone, temperature and halogen loading, and (c) tropospheric ozone and related chemical processes.</p> <p>Scientific achievements:</p> <p>Three major field campaigns to retrieve firn air and ice spanning 100 - 200 years of atmospheric compositional history were carried out at NGRIP Greenland, and Berkner Island and Law Dome, Antarctica. A continuous two-year experiment to study the transport of gases in to and through firn at Halley, Antarctica was also carried out to improve our ability to reconstruct long-term time trends of the target gases from firn and ice profile. Analyses of NGRIP firn air showed this to be the most successful Northern Hemispheric (NH) firn air campaign undertaken anywhere to date. NGRIP is less perturbed by <i>in-situ</i> chemical effects than previously reported Arctic firn profiles. More than 90% of all pollutant gases are released in the NH, but conditions for preserving trace gases in firn and ice in the North are usually less suitable than in Antarctica (lesser extent of glacial ice, warmer temperatures, etc.). This unique record from NGRIP is, therefore, highly valuable, especially for shorter-lived gases that are mostly confined to the hemisphere in which they are emitted.</p> <p>Measurements from Berkner Island and Law Dome have also provided essential information. Comparing trends from both hemispheres, furthermore, has yielded considerable information on the origins and atmospheric lifetimes of the gases studied, and on their global distributions. Long-lived ODSs and GHGs can be studied in both Arctic and Antarctic firn. Firn air records tend to be older and better preserved in the Antarctic. Berkner Island and Law Dome represent very different glacial environments: the former having a relatively low rate of snow deposition and the latter very high. Conformity of reconstructed trends between such different environments provides significant confidence in the reconstructed histories of the gases.</p> <p>A general and important overall finding of CRYOSTAT has been that our present day atmosphere is chemically entirely different from that of the pre-industrial Earth. Increases – usually large increases - have taken place in the abundance of nearly every gas that we have measured (and we have measured more than sixty), even amongst those that also have natural sources. A few gases have exhibited decreases in the last one or two decades due to changing industrial practices, but still remain above pre-industrial levels. Of the ODSs the only gases with significant pre-industrial concentrations are methyl chloride and methyl bromide, plus a small contribution from chloroform, bromoform and some other minor halomethanes. Of the GHGs, those with pre-industrial backgrounds are carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and carbon tetrafluoride (CF₄). Non-methane hydrocarbons and oxides of nitrogen (as measured by proxy from increased levels of organic nitrates) have also risen substantially since the mid-1950s: likely accounting for what is reported in other studies as a probable doubling or trebling of tropospheric ozone in the NH during the 20th century.</p> <p>Some specific outcomes include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The sum of reactive chlorine in the troposphere and stratosphere from all source gases (CCl_y) has increased almost eight-fold since pre-industrial times, while the sum of reactive bromine (CBr_y) has more than doubled. Effective equivalent stratospheric chlorine (EESC) from a combination of both chlorine and bromine source gases has, likewise, increased during this time by a factor of five. • Century-long trends of stratospheric ozone and temperature have been derived from the above. The onset of the Antarctic ozone hole in the 1980s has been shown to be accounted for by a model utilising these observed parameters. Ozone loss due to gas-phase reactions reached 40% of pre-industrial values in near-polar areas at about 45 km altitude, although there was evidence for some offset of this damage by ‘self-healing’ of ozone levels at lower altitudes. Stratospheric temperatures were modelled to have decreased by as much as 7°C by 1998 due to loss of ozone at this altitude. 			

- The atmospheric lifetimes of many halocarbons are not constant but have varied over time according to their emission histories. In some cases these variations can be pronounced: for example the lifetime of Halon 1301 is calculated to have been 88 years in 1975, but only 58 years in 2002. This has profound implications for the calculation of Ozone Depletion Potentials and Global Warming Potentials.
- The polar trends of halocarbons with lifetimes of less than about a decade are dependent on the location of their principal emissions, as demonstrated by the reconstructed trends of short-lived halon gases. In the case of halons 1211 and 1202 a shift in emissions from North America/Western Europe to China is consistent with observations in the firm air records from Greenland.
- Chloroform has a smaller natural source than previously thought, and has declined in concentration in the last two decades because of changes in paper and pulp manufacture. Other bromine-containing trihalomethanes have previously unrealised anthropogenic sources, possibly from water chlorination.
- The perfluorocarbon “super” greenhouse gases are all almost exclusively of anthropogenic origin, with the notable exception of CF₄. CF₄, however, also has an important source from aluminium smelting, as does C₂F₆. The trends of these two latter gases are, however, changing, as emissions from aluminium smelting decrease while emissions from the electronics industry increase.
- The direct radiative forcing of the halocarbon gases due to their change in concentration from pre-industrial times to 2002 is calculated to be 327 mW m⁻². The amount due to the fluorinated “super” greenhouse gases alone (which are not controlled by the Montreal Protocol) is 17 mW m⁻². That due to CO₂ over the same period is 1460 mW m⁻¹, for CH₄ 486 mW m⁻¹, and for N₂O 156 mW m⁻¹. Radiative forcing due to the super GHGs has, however, been rising at an ever increasing rate, whereas that due to CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O has been rising at a decreasing rate. Furthermore, several of these fluorinated gases have thousand year lifetimes or more, and may become significant in the future in the absence of measures to reduce their emissions.
- Ozone cannot be measured directly in either firm or ice, but increased levels of other gases, non-methane hydrocarbons, and alkyl nitrates, are ‘smoking guns’ of increased tropospheric NO_x and increased ozone.
- Novel isotopic measurements of CH₄ and CO have shown that man-induced biomass burning has likely been a significant factor in the observed increased concentrations of these gases. In the case of CO this is the first time that a 20th century trend of this gas has been measured. It is an important player in the atmospheric chemistry that affects the lifetimes of other GHGs and ODSs. For CH₄ there is also clear evidence in its isotope ratios for an enhanced loss process due to oxidation by increased levels of stratospheric chlorine.
- Also entirely novel has been the complete isotopic measurements of N₂O (including position-dependent isotope ratios) pointing to the equal importance of natural and synthetic fertilizers as the prime causes of the observed persistent rise in atmospheric N₂O.
- Process studies have allowed a better quantitative understanding of the manner in which gases move through firm and become encapsulated in ice, thereby significantly improving our ability to interpret ice core records, not only for the time period studied under CRYOSTAT, but of all time scales for which glacial records exist. This is now enabling important questions concerning climate-chemistry feedbacks during climatic cycles to be addressed.

Socio-economic relevance and policy implications:

Climate change and stratospheric ozone depletion are two of the most pressing environmental problems of the day. The anthropogenic causes of these are largely attributable to emissions of gases from industrial processes, power production, refrigeration, biomass burning, agriculture, etc. CRYOSTAT has shown the extent to which human influences have perturbed the natural, pre-industrial composition and chemistry of the atmosphere to produce the atmosphere that we live in today. It has investigated the sources of individual gases, the relative contribution of natural and manmade sources, and has assessed the contributions to stratospheric ozone destruction and/or atmospheric warming of gases individually and in aggregate. It has shown the ameliorating effects of the Montreal Protocol, but illustrates that conditions are as precariously balanced with regard to ozone hole formation as they have ever been. The majority of GHGs, meanwhile, continue to rise including those with lifetimes that span generations. This provides a firm platform from which to judge the efficacy of continued adherence to the Montreal Protocol and the coming implementation of the Kyoto Protocol, and contributes to the scientific underpinning of them both.

Conclusions:

Widespread and dramatic changes in the atmospheric composition of GHGs and ODSs in both hemispheres, and notably the Northern Hemisphere, during the 20th century have been clearly demonstrated by CRYOSTAT measurements.

Keywords: firm, ice, atmosphere, greenhouse gases, ozone depleting substances, climate change, stratospheric ozone, radiative forcing, atmospheric chemistry, Arctic, Antarctic, ozone, O₃, carbon dioxide, CO₂, methane, CH₄, nitrous oxide, N₂O, carbon monoxide, CO, halocarbons, CFCs, HCFCs, HFCs, PFCs, CF₄, Montreal Protocol, Kyoto Protocol

SECTION 6: DETAILED REPORT RELATED TO THE OVERALL PROJECT DURATION

6.1 BACKGROUND

Two of the most pressing environmental problems of the day are human-induced climate change and stratospheric ozone depletion. The latter itself also has profound implications for climate, in addition to the better-known direct impacts on human health and ecosystem vitality. Both are largely the result of the release of numerous gases to the atmosphere from anthropogenic sources. Some such gases are strong infrared absorbers or “greenhouse” gases (GHGs), others are ozone-depleting substances (ODSs). Although the Montreal Protocol, to which the EU is committed, has been successful in curtailing the release of some ODSs, others continue to rise. Even more intractable is the rise of GHGs, despite the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, to which the EU is a signatory and the proposals to cut emissions under the Kyoto agreement, which all countries of the EU have ratified. Still other gases are precursors of tropospheric ozone, which is itself a powerful GHG, or they may interfere with the natural oxidation cycles responsible for removing many other GHGs and ODSs from the atmosphere. Natural emissions of GHGs and ODSs, and natural processes affecting their distribution, are also an important factor in determining the health of the ozone layer. Yet the degree to which the natural chemistry-climate system has been perturbed by human activity is poorly known. The changing nature of sources, such as soils, wetlands, vegetation, and marine microorganisms, and sinks such as atmospheric oxidation, oceanic and terrestrial uptake, etc. are little understood, yet are themselves sensitive to climate change, past and future. By reconstructing the evolution of the present polluted atmosphere from its “clean” pre-industrial beginnings we hope to better understand how the chemical composition of the Earth’s atmosphere has changed to the presence of mankind on the face of the planet, and hence better predict how it may change in future. CRYOSTAT, therefore, contributes to the scientific underpinning of required to predict the climatic effects due to changing industrial (and natural) emissions, and hence to better plan for the social and economic consequences of such change.

Studies of stratospheric ozone depletion and climate change leading to remedial policies have clear and apparent benefits to European social objectives. The development of an Arctic ozone hole in recent years, and noticeable thinning of mid-latitudinal stratospheric ozone, has led to increased UV fluxes over Europe. A breakdown in the implementation of the Montreal Protocol process could lead to significantly enhanced UV fluxes over Europe. Such increases would likely result in human health effects, including increased sunburn, excess skin damage and cancers, cataracts, and immune system suppression. Damage would also be suffered by livestock and by commercial crops, as well as by natural fauna and flora. UV penetration in to water bodies has the ability to disrupt food chains, notably by impacts on phytoplankton. Increased UV also results in damage to many exterior construction materials adding maintenance and replacement costs. Higher UV can potentially change the photochemical state of the troposphere, enhancing photochemical smog and ozone production in the lower atmosphere with direct effects on human health (respiratory disease), and indirect effects on climate (ozone and aerosol production).

It is still a controversial issue as to whether deleterious effects have already impacted Europe from stratospheric ozone reductions, but there is no dispute that the global ozone layer “is currently in its most vulnerable state” (Scientific Assessment of Ozone Depletion 1998, WMO, 1999). The occurrence of Arctic ozone holes is influenced by climate, and with stratospheric chlorine-bromine loadings at peak levels, an unusually cold or protracted winter in the Arctic stratosphere could easily trigger a substantial loss of springtime ozone behind the polar front which, both before and after break-up, may affect much of Europe. There is, therefore, a critical need to understand the evolution of stratosphere ozone chemistry from its pre-industrial natural state to its present perturbed state, so that the threat from continued growth of ozone-depleting substances and the efficacy of remedial measures could be assessed.

Table 1. Overview of principal GHGs, ODSs, and related gases measured by CRYOSTAT

Gas [†]	ODS/GHG	Man-made and natural sources	Sinks	Comments
CO ₂	GHG	Fossil fuel combustion, biomass burning, deforestation, oceans, terrestrial biosphere, volcanism, CH ₄ and CO oxidation	Uptake by oceans and biosphere	Principal anthropogenic GHG, partitioning uncertain and variable
CH ₄	GHG *1	Ruminant animals, rice paddies, gas and mining leaks, landfill, biomass burning, anaerobic decomposition	Tropospheric oxidation, stratospheric Cl	Major anthropogenic GHG
N ₂ O	GHG ODS	Land cultivation, fertiliser use, oceans, soils, aquifers	Stratospheric oxidation/O ¹ D	Major anthropogenic GHG: 'missing' global source(s)
CO	*1	Fossil fuel burning, biomass burning, CH ₄ and hydrocarbon oxidation, oceans	Tropospheric oxidation	Global budget not closed, O ₃ precursor
COS	GHG	Fossil fuel and biomass burning, soils, oceans, oxidation of CS ₂ (from wetlands, artificial fibre industry, etc.)	Tropospheric and stratospheric oxidation	Forms aerosols in stratosphere
CFCs	ODS GHG	Refrigeration and air conditioning, foam blowing, aerosol propellants, electronics industry	Stratospheric photolysis	Direct and indirect effects on radiative balance (changes in stratospheric ozone)
HCFCs	ODS GHG	Similar to the CFCs which they replace	Stratospheric oxidation, photolysis, tropospheric oxidation	
HFCs	GHG	Similar to CFCs, also chemical industry	Stratospheric, tropospheric oxidation	
Halons	ODS	Fire extinguishers	Stratospheric, tropospheric photolysis	Direct and indirect effects on radiative balance (as CFCs)
PFCs	GHG	Aluminium smelting, chemical industry, geochemical	Semi-permanent gases	Large global warming potentials (GWPs)
SF ₆ SF ₂ CF ₃	GHG	Magnesium smelting, electrical insulation, leak detection, organofluorine production	Very long-lived gases	Very large GWPs
CH ₃ Cl	ODS	Fossil fuel combustion and incineration, chemical industry, oceans, biomass burning, terrestrial biosphere	Stratospheric photolysis, tropospheric oxidation	Atmospheric budget poorly constrained
CCl ₄ CH ₂ Cl ₂ CHCl ₃ , etc.	ODS	Chemical industry, dry cleaning, industrial solvents, fossil fuel combustion, biomass burning, oceans, soils	Stratospheric photolysis, tropospheric oxidation	Atmospheric budgets poorly constrained in many cases
CH ₃ Br	ODS	Fumigant, vehicle exhaust, oceans, soils	Tropospheric oxidation, oceans, soils	Atmospheric budget poorly constrained
RBr/I		Oceans	Tropospheric oxidation and photolysis	Indicators of marine primary productivity
NMHC	*1	Fossil fuel combustion, biomass burning, gas and mining leaks, agriculture, oceans	Tropospheric oxidation	Tropospheric ozone precursors
RONO ₂	*1	Secondary pollutants from hydrocarbons and NO ₂ , oceans	Tropospheric thermolysis, oxidation	Indicators of NO _x and ozone chemistry

[†]R refers to an alkyl group; *1. Indirect effects via changes in tropospheric ozone and oxidative lifetimes of key gases

Likewise there are manifold impacts that may ensue from climate change in Europe (not all necessarily deleterious), again affecting agricultural productivity (changes in rainfall patterns, temperature extremes, migration of pests), human well-being (extreme weather events, flooding, storm surges, avalanches, etc), and economy (construction, aviation and road transport, agriculture, fisheries, coastal defences, etc.). There are also important synergies between stratospheric ozone depletion and climate change. There is a close radiative and chemical coupling between the troposphere and stratosphere such warming of the troposphere has been paralleled by cooling of the stratosphere. This latter effect raises the probability of polar ozone hole development. Likewise, since ozone is itself a radiatively important gas, thinning ozone in the stratosphere, and increased levels at the ground, may both tend to enhance the direct radiative forcing effect.

The seriousness of potential climate change has been underlined by strong statements in the most recent IPCC assessment (Third Assessment Report "Climate Change 2001: The Scientific Basis", Shanghai, 2001) that climate change over the last 50 years is indeed "likely to have been due to increases in greenhouse gas concentrations"; with predictions of far more pronounced changes to come. It is against this background of concern for the future state of the atmosphere that this study of the impact of industrialisation on the evolution of atmospheric composition, chemistry and climate up to the present day is set.

6.2 SCIENTIFIC/TECHNOLOGICAL AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC OBJECTIVES

CRYOSTAT has employed an holistic approach to deconvolute the identity, both natural and man-made, and changing sources strengths of essentially all significant GHGs (other than water vapour), ODSs, and related trace gases in the atmosphere on time scales that effectively cover the time span over which their emissions have grown as a result of anthropogenic activities. This was achieved by reconstructing their global atmospheric compositional histories from cryospheric records (firn air and ice cores), by determining correlations between hemispheres and between different gases, and by employing atmospheric models to explore source-sink relationships and to reconstruct other non-measured chemical species and parameters. Powerful interpretive tools have arisen from the measurements of stable isotopes of several gases, including some novel isotopic measurements of CH₄, N₂O, and CO in ice and firn. Isotope ratios can yield information on the various modes of production of the gases (notably between biological and non-biological origins), and on their atmospheric sink processes. Since sources/sinks to and from the atmosphere are often common to a number of gases (e.g. biomass burning, atmospheric oxidation, etc.), this isotopic information also provides a generic interpretive tool.

CRYOSTAT was implemented through a series of combined firn and shallow ice drilling expeditions, providing the first ever such set of comprehensive gas measurements in contiguous firn and ice profiles from both hemispheres (i.e. Greenland and Antarctica). The extraction and measurement of multiple gas species from ice was one of the major innovative aspects and technological challenges of the project. Year-round field studies were also conducted in Antarctica to study the mechanisms controlling transport of atmospheric chemical constituents across the air-snow interface. This allowed us to refine existing firn air transport models, notably to account for thermal diffusion and convection effects in the upper firn, and so ensure accurate conversion of depth profiles into temporal trends. Year round measurements also helped define the seasonal cycle of shorter-lived gases, crucial for the proper interpretation and validation of firn and atmospheric chemistry models.

Combining firn modelling with atmospheric modelling we were then able to convert concentration-depth profiles at single geographic points (i.e. the polar drill sites) first into local time trends, and then into hemispheric/global time-varying latitudinal and altitudinal (troposphere and stratosphere) distributions of species. The reconstructed trends were further used in additional modelling work to explore the impacts of CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, and halocarbon increases on stratospheric Cl_y, Br_y, ozone, and temperature over the last century or more. Other models were used to examine source-sink relationships for N₂O and CH₄.

As a final step in this sequence of interpretive studies, the potential impact of these changes on the radiative forcing of climate during the period of 19th and 20th century industrialisation was determined. Radiative forcing due to individual target molecules was assessed using detailed line-by-line and narrow band radiative transfer codes.

The outputs of CRYOSTAT consist of a database (ultimately to become freely and publicly accessible through a central on-line server) of global trends of numerous key atmospheric gases, from pre-industrial times to 2001. It also includes assessments of the consequent impacts of these changes on radiative forcing, on stratospheric composition, chemistry, and temperature, and on the fluxes of certain key gases between environmental compartments. It has produced a set of refined modelling tools of wider utility to the atmospheric chemistry, global climate and glaciological research communities. It has provided various improved techniques for determining gaseous composition from firn and ice cores. Finally, and most significantly, it has improved the state of knowledge on interactions between atmospheric chemistry and climate, which will in turn improve the predictive capability of climate modellers, with important implications for policy-makers.

There are critical economic considerations involved in adopting abatement measures in Europe to counter ozone depletion and climate change. Such measures may be very costly in terms of either emission reduction technology, or development of alternative substances or technologies, although such measures may also create new manufacturing and employment opportunities. A notable issue is the European Union commitment resulting from the Kyoto Agreement to cut CO₂ (or equivalent CO₂). To cut emissions of CO₂ itself will require expensive CO₂ emission control devices, energy saving measures with complex economic repercussions both positive and negative, or an increased reliance on non-combustive power generation (nuclear, hydroelectric, and alternative).

A complementary strategy would be to reduce emissions of non-CO₂ greenhouse gases such as methane, N₂O, tropospheric ozone, HFCs and HCFCs (the latter are already subject to constraints under the Montreal Protocol), and long-lived fluorinated gases such as SF₆ and CF₄. These may prove to be less costly and more easily realised than reducing CO₂ alone, at least in the short term. Conversely, not regulating emissions of such gases may undermine efforts to control climate forcing through CO₂ emissions abatement. Again, it is only by understanding the evolution of the anthropogenic greenhouse effects, its links to GHG emissions, and the contributions of natural and anthropogenic sources and sinks, that the cost effectiveness of potential amelioration strategies can be assessed. The various natural and man-made origins of methane, nitrous oxide, and ozone, three of the most important greenhouse gases are, for example, still very poorly understood. Individual source strengths of several halogenated GHGs are incompletely known, whilst CF₄ for instance, has controversially been claimed to have natural as well as industrial origins. The long term trend of tropospheric ozone has, to date, largely been a matter of conjecture and deduction.

Similar issues exist with ozone depleters. There has, for example, been much controversy regarding methyl bromide, an agricultural pesticide. Whereas the growth rates of many chlorinated ODSs have begun to decline, bromine in the stratosphere continues to rise almost unabated, and there are concerns regarding illegal production of controlled ODSs, and production of novel ODSs. Global warming could even, indirectly, affect natural sources of ODSs such as methyl chloride, methyl bromide and bromoform. All of these issues lead to uncertainties regarding the time for recovery of the ozone-layer to its 'natural' state (or, at least, pre-Antarctic ozone hole conditions), which even optimistic estimates place as being towards the middle of this century.

Certainly there are potentially enormous costs associated with a strategy of inaction. Economic losses from natural disasters increased from \$53 billion per year in the 1960's to \$480 billion per year in the 1990's, of which 80% of the losses were weather-related, and therefore sensitive to climate change. A. Mayer and T. Cooper (*Environmental Finance*, 1(7), 19-21, 2000) have conjectured that should such trends continue ("business as usual" scenario), global economic losses could exceed Gross Domestic Product (GDP) by the year 2065, at a monetary value of over US\$200 trillion at today's prices. Although these projections are perhaps intentionally provocative, they do serve as a reminder that the understanding and mitigation of global atmospheric change goes to the core of European, and indeed global, prosperity, human well-being, and sustainable growth.

INNOVATIONS IN CRYOSTAT

In the original CRYOSTAT Description of Work we anticipated that a number of novel and significant new measurements, methodologies, discoveries and interpretations would emerge from the project. Here we revisit this list and add further, in some cases unexpected, important findings and developments from CRYOSTAT studies.

- First measurements of multiple trace gases (CFCs, CF₄ and other perfluorocarbons, CCl₄, ethane, alkyl nitrates, etc.) in air occluded in glacial ice.
- First contiguous measurements of trace gases through firn and shallow ice yielding complete histories of these gases from pre-industrial times to the present day.
- Comprehensive measurements of more than sixty trace gases in deep polar firn, demonstrating that whilst a few gases have a natural background, the majority are of man-made origin, and almost all have increased in the atmosphere in the last century.
- First comprehensive measurements of trace gases in firn from the Northern Hemisphere (where more than 90% of pollutants are released) including many for which there was no previous long-term record at all in that hemisphere (e.g. non-methane hydrocarbons, alkyl nitrates, short-lived bromo and chlorocarbons).
- First long term measurements of ‘parent-daughter’ hydrocarbons and nitrated products illustrating that reactive nitrogen levels must have increased in the Northern Hemisphere which would have substantially increased tropospheric ozone (a powerful greenhouse gas in the lower atmosphere) there.
- Assembly of a complete history of reactive chlorine and bromine in the troposphere and stratosphere during the 20th century showing that stratospheric chlorine has increased more than eight-fold since preindustrial times and bromine doubled.
- From the above, century-long trends of stratospheric ozone and temperature have been derived and the onset of the Antarctic ozone hole shown to be accounted for in a model utilising these parameters.
- Model demonstration that for gases with stratospheric sinks, a single value of atmospheric lifetime is not appropriate, but instead it varies with growth rate.
- Derivation of a 20th century history of direct radiative forcing (global warming) due to halogenated trace gases showing the alarming increase in radiative forcing due to very long-lived gases (i.e. those with lifetimes of thousands of years).
- Significant improvements have been made to calculated radiative efficiency factors of several gases including, in some cases, new measurements of their infrared cross sections.
- First measurement of the evolution of $\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{H}_4$ over the last two centuries suggesting an increasing source from biomass burning, and also demonstrating the coupling between methane oxidation and increased chlorine in the stratosphere.
- First comprehensive reconstruction of N₂O isotopic change (nitrogen isotope ratios, oxygen isotope ratios and even position-dependent nitrogen isotope ratios) pointing to the importance of fertilizer use as a prime cause for the upturn in atmospheric N₂O.
- First demonstration, from a novel combination of isotopic signatures and concentration measurements, that the important pollutant carbon monoxide (CO) has increased in the Southern Hemisphere since the early 20th century, most likely due to man-induced biomass burning. CO is an important player in the atmospheric chemistry that regulates many other greenhouse gases and ozone-depletors.
- First comparative measurements of trace gases in ice and firn from low and very high accumulation-rate sites.

- First simultaneous year-round measurements of trace gases in the lower Antarctic atmosphere and upper firn, yielding some of the first ever Antarctic seasonal cycles of some of the gases, and the means to test for conservative transport of gases in to the firn record.
- Year-round measurements of isotopic and elemental ratios of permanent gases in firn to allow thermal diffusion effects to be determined and implemented in firn air transport models.
- Studies of fractionation effects at the firn-ice transition, showing these to be highly significant for small atomic/molecular radius gases, but with an upper cut-off at a collision diameter of about 3.6 Å.
- Measurements of multiple isotope ratios are providing important new constraints to the modelling of past (paleo) firn thickness, thereby allowing accurate ice core dating and a far better understanding of synchronicities between atmospheric gases and temperature changes. This has been of significant benefit to paleoclimate science.
- Important improvements in ice extraction and analysis have been developed including novel continuous on-line techniques for water isotopes, and also on-line isotopes of gases: the former of interest in wider field of water analysis (hydrology, medical sciences, etc.).